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Review Article

Diagnostic Challenges in Pancreatic Tumors

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Abstract

Background: Pancreatic tumors have a large diversity, with an increasing incidence and mortality. Although the diagnosis methods have improved in recent years, establishing a diagnosis and a histopathological type of pancreatic tumor can still pose a challenge.

Aim: We propose to present a concise list of difficulties regarding the clinical, biological, and imagistic diagnosis of pancreatic tumors.

Key information: The clinical manifestations of pancreatic tumors depend on their location and size, on the presence of metastatic lesions, but the difficulty of orientation towards this diagnosis is determined by the fact that most lesions are asymptomatic or present in the early stages of non-specific symptoms. The usual biological parameters are non-specific in pancreatic tumors in the early stages, but studies are underway regarding a series of biomarkers, genetic micro-sequences, or inorganic nanomaterials that could be used in the early diagnosis of pancreatic cancers. An essential stage in the diagnosis of pancreatic tumors is represented by imaging investigations, which are associated with endoscopic and tumor biopsy procedures and can outline a picture regarding the presence of the tumor at the level of the pancreas, the relationship with the neighboring organs, the nature of the tumor and the histopathological type. There are a series of indications and limitations regarding each of these investigations, trying to develop various algorithms for the diagnosis of pancreatic tumors.

Conclusion: The medical research conducted to develop new diagnostic procedures has the objective of ensuring an early diagnosis of pancreatic tumors, in a stage that offers the best chances of recovery for the patient.

Introduction

Pancreatic tumors can present a wide spectrum. Various classifications divide them into primitive or secondary tumors, benign or malignant tumors, solid, cystic, or mixed tumors, exocrine (epithelial), and endocrine or mixed-origin tumors.

Several clinical studies have highlighted an increase in both the incidence and mortality of pancreatic tumors [1-5]. Also, the advances made in recent years in medical imaging have led to more frequent discovery of these types of tumors [6,7]. However, establishing the diagnosis of a pancreatic tumor and its histopathological type can often prove difficult.

Diagnostic challenges in pancreatic tumors

Screening: Regarding the screening of pancreatic tumors, a higher risk for the development of pancreatic neoplasia has been demonstrated among patients with a

family history of pancreatitis or pancreatic cancer [8-10], Peutz-Jeghers syndrome [11], hereditary nonpolyposis colorectal cancer (HNPCC) [12], familial syndrome of atypical nevi [13] or mutations of BRCA-2 gene [11,14-16]. However, patients from these risk groups represent only a small proportion of all pancreatic neoplasms, up to 5% - 10%, so screening using this algorithm is not feasible, and the efficiency/cost ratio is low [17,18]. Some studies have also been conducted on various screening methods regarding the correlation between pancreatic cancer and newly discovered diabetes [18-22], respectively glucose intolerance as an early manifestation of pancreatic cancer in a resectable stage [18,21,23-25].

Clinical diagnosis: The clinical manifestations of pancreatic tumors depend on their location and size, on the presence of metastatic lesions, but the difficulty of orientation towards this diagnosis is determined by the fact that most lesions are asymptomatic or present in the early stages non-specific symptoms such as abdominal

pain, nausea, vomiting, fatigue, the differential diagnosis being imposed with a series of diseases from the biliary, gastroduodenal or cardiovascular areas [26-28]. Thus, the diagnosis of pancreatic tumors is made most of the time in advanced stages. In the case of malignant tumors, more than half of the patients present metastases and only approximately 8% of the tumors are localized [29].

Biological diagnosis: The usual biological parameters are non-specific in pancreatic tumors in the early stages, suggesting this diagnosis with the onset of the icteric syndrome in tumors located in the head of the pancreas, respectively with the appearance of protein depletion in the advanced stages. In pancreatic neoplasms, the most used marker is cancer antigen 19-9 (CA 19-9), with a sensitivity and specificity that can reach up to 90% in the case of symptomatic patients, values over 100 U/mL suggesting an unresectable tumor or the presence of metastatic disease [30,31]. Another use of this marker is the prognostic role in monitoring tumor recurrence after pancreatic resections. However, CA 19-9 is not used as a screening method, having a positive predictive value between 0.5% - 0.9% [32]. This marker can also be present in other inflammatory or obstructive hepatobiliary diseases, in other pancreatic diseases, as well as in various other cancers. In addition, in patients with a negative Lewis blood phenotype, CA 19-9 will have low values, even in advanced pancreatic neoplasms [17].

In case of suspicion of a pancreatic neuroendocrine tumor, a series of biological markers can be determined, such as chromogranin A, neuron-specific enolase, pancreatic polypeptide, human chorionic gonadotropin, alpha-fetoprotein, gastrin, insulin, glucagon, somatostatin or intestinal vasoactive peptide. They are not routinely analyzed, but they can guide the diagnosis of this type of tumors [33-36]. Currently, studies are underway regarding a series of biomarkers, genetic micro-sequences, or inorganic nanomaterials that could be used in the early diagnosis of pancreatic cancers [37-40]. One such example is the serum value of macrophage inhibitory cytokine 1 (MIC-1), which proved a high sensitivity for the diagnosis of pancreatic adenocarcinoma, especially in association with CA 19-9 values [17,41].

Imagistic diagnosis: An essential stage in the diagnosis of pancreatic tumors is represented by imaging investigations, which are associated with endoscopic and tumor biopsy procedures and can outline a picture regarding the presence of the tumor at the level of the pancreas, the relationship with the neighboring organs, the nature of the tumor and the histopathological type. There are a series of indications and limitations regarding each of these investigations, trying to develop various algorithms for the diagnosis of pancreatic tumors, such an example is highlighted in Figure 1.

Numerous protocols and studies have suggested Computed Tomography as the first imaging investigation for the detection of pancreatic tumors, especially the multi-detector variant (MDCT) [17,42]. Pancreatic neoplastic lesions are described on the CT scan as poorly defined tumoral masses, which are enhanced less with contrast substance compared to the adjacent parenchyma. Other changes highly specific to pancreatic neoplasms include dilatation of the main bile duct, pancreatic contour abnormalities, distal pancreatic atrophy, disruptions/dilatations of the Wirsung duct, or pancreatic hypoattenuation [17,43]. Computer tomography is also useful for the staging of pancreatic neoplasms, especially regarding the involvement of the mesenteric artery and vein, as well as the celiac trunk, with implications on tumor resectability [44-47]. In addition, the CT scan can highlight the presence of peritoneal carcinomatosis, ascites, carcinomatous epiploitis, or pulmonary metastases [17,46].

Limitations of the CT scan include patients with renal impairment or risk of nephrotoxicity, as well as exposure to a significant radiation dose [17]. Also, the enhancement with contrast substance of the pancreatic parenchyma can be influenced by the concentration of the solution used, the injection rate, the age, the degree of obesity of the patient, or the presence of congestive heart failure [48].

Pancreatic lipomatosis, found especially in elderly patients with obesity or diabetes, can be seen as a focal hypodense mass on the CT scan, being difficult to differentiate from a malignant lesion, in which case the suggested exam is the abdominal MRI [49]. Also, chronic focal pancreatitis is often difficult to differentiate from pancreatic cancer on CT or MRI examinations and can be described as a mass that obstructs the bile or pancreatic duct. The investigations that can differentiate the two conditions are represented by EUS elastography and contrast-enhanced EUS, as well as EUS with FNA [44]. Another disease whose differential diagnosis with pancreatic cancer on the CT scan can be difficult to achieve is autoimmune pancreatitis, which usually has a diffuse pancreatic predisposition, but can also present as a localized pancreatic mass [44,50]. For differentiation, positron emission tomography (PET/CT)

using 18-fluorodeoxyglucose (18FDG) as a contrast agent, EUS with FNA [51,52], or serum levels of immunoglobulin 4 (Ig4) are used. Ig4 has a high specificity for autoimmune pancreatitis, with values usually at least twice the normal value, in contrast to pancreatic cancer, where Ig4 has slightly increased values in approximately 7% of cases [50,53]. In addition, unlike pancreatic cancer, autoimmune pancreatitis usually responds to steroid treatment [54].

The MRI examination can be used instead of computed tomography for the diagnosis of pancreatic tumors in patients with renal failure, with a history of allergy to iodinated contrast material, or as a second-line imaging investigation when there is a high clinical suspicion for a pancreatic lesion that is not detectable on CT scan. It also can provide additional information on hepatic tumors identified on the CT scan [17]. The MRI examination can detect early the presence of a pancreatic tumor, providing information on alterations of the pancreas or the Wirsung duct or information regarding local invasion, the specificity and sensitivity for pancreatic cancer being located at approximately 89% [55]. However, numerous studies have failed to show a clear benefit compared to CT examination, which is added to the high costs and more difficult accessibility compared to computed tomography [17]. In the context of the development of digital imaging techniques, a recent study suggested that the GRE (Gradient Echo Sequences) MRI exam, using 3D technology, combined with MR cholangiopancreatography (MRCP) would provide superior results to MDCT regarding pancreatic tumor detection and similar results regarding evaluation of the resectability of a neoplastic lesion [56,57].

PET/CT with 18FDG has been shown to have no benefit in the usual diagnosis of pancreatic tumors compared to CT or MRI examinations [17]. Although it was hoped that it could differentiate chronic pancreatitis from neoplastic lesions, this was not the case due to similar uptake of the radiotracer in the two conditions [58]. The usefulness of PET/CT in pancreatic tumors is described in the detection of metastases, especially bone metastases [59], as well as in the tumor response to chemotherapy and radiotherapy, by measuring changes in radiotracer uptake before and after performing these procedures [60,61].

Although frequently used in the past, the role of endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP) in the diagnosis of pancreatic tumors decreased with the development of imaging methods [62,63], having these investigations the supplementary risk of developing complications such as digestive perforations or acute pancreatitis [64]. There are currently several promising studies analyzing the obtaining of cytological samples during ERCP using an endoscopic naso-pancreatic tube, which is placed in the Wirsung canal, aspirating pancreatic juice repeatedly, a technique called SPACE ("serial pancreatic juice aspiration cytologic examination") [65-67].

Endoscopic ultrasound is another procedure used in the diagnosis of pancreatic tumors, thanks to the high-resolution images, being especially useful in small tumors [65]. Usual EUS has a sensitivity of 98% in the diagnosis of small pancreatic neoplasms, better compared to a sensitivity of 86% in computed tomography ($p = 0.012$) [68]. In particular, in the case of pancreatic tumors with a maximum diameter of 30 mm, EUS has a sensitivity of 93%, compared to the sensitivity of 67% of MRI or 53% of computed tomography [69]. Also, EUS has a better sensitivity than CT examination (67% vs. 41%, $p < 0.001$) in terms of local tumor staging [68], with the mention of a limitation regarding tumor invasion at the level of the superior mesenteric artery and vein due to their distance from the probe [70,71]. In the case of pancreatic neuroendocrine tumors, which are characterized by hypervascularization, EUS with a Doppler signal can be useful in establishing the diagnosis, unlike pancreatic adenocarcinoma, which usually presents local hypovascularization [63].

Elastography can be used to diagnose pancreatic tumors, [72,73], but is non-specific in the initial tumor stages due to the distribution of tissue elasticity [63,72]. Regarding the diagnosis of pancreatic cancer, various meta-analytic studies have highlighted a sensitivity of 95% - 97%, but with a specificity of only 67% - 76% [74,75].

EUS with intravenously administered contrast is a promising modality for the diagnosis of pancreatic tumors, with meta-analytic studies suggesting a sensitivity of 94% and a specificity of 89% for the diagnosis of pancreatic cancer [76]. This procedure may also be useful when there is a high risk of bleeding using fine needle aspiration [63].

EUS associated with pancreatic FNA is currently a common modality for the diagnosis of pancreatic tumors detected by other imaging methods such as CT or MRI. Recent studies suggest a sensitivity of 86% - 91% and a specificity of 94% - 99% for the diagnosis of a pancreatic mass [77-79]. In addition, the superiority of FNA using EUS compared to FNA using abdominal ultrasound was found in terms of the quality of the samples obtained, the rate of complications being similar [80]. There are also several limitations of this procedure, regarding the type of needle used, the experience of the endoscopist, or the presence of a pathologist to perform an extemporaneous histopathological examination [63].

Conclusion

Pancreatic tumors present a diagnostic challenge, both in tumoral detection and in establishing a histopathological type.

Clinical manifestations and usual biological parameters are non-specific in early tumoral stages, but several markers are currently studied regarding the early diagnosis

of pancreatic cancer. Imagistic diagnostic procedures encompass computer tomography, magnetic resonance imaging, and endoscopic ultrasound with fine needle aspiration, but each of them has certain limitations and diagnostic algorithms have been proposed.

The medical research conducted to develop new diagnostic procedures has the objective of ensuring an early diagnosis of pancreatic tumors, in a stage that offers the best chances of recovery for the patient.

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